

ChainPro – A Web3 Platform for Artists

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Abstract

Blockchain Technology and Web3 solutions act as catalysts for innovation and creativity, providing artists with tools to experiment with new business models, services, and applications, free from the constraints of centralized entities. Digital innovation significantly impacts artists' ability to connect and create trusted communities, leveraging these technologies.

Several platforms support the digitalization of creative arts, but Web3 platforms can revolutionize the sector by simplifying blockchain adoption, enabling the formation of Decentralized Autonomous Organization (DAOs), fostering innovative business models, enhancing legal transparency, nurturing communities, and driving creativity and competitiveness.

This paper explores how Blockchain, Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs), and related Web3 technologies can empower Creators by providing greater ownership and control over their creative works. A state-of-the-art analysis identifies the technical requirements for integrating blockchain and NFT-based services for user engagement and innovative business models. Additionally, a user-centred design approach was adopted to collect user requirements for managing creative works ownership, Intellectual Property Rights and revenue distribution through smart contracts.

The results led to the implementation and validation of ChainPro for Artists (ChainPro4Artists), a Web3 innovative platform that supports advanced blockchain technologies, including Layer 2 infrastructures (e.g., Polygon) and DAOs tailored for artist communities.

1. Introduction

Current digital platforms are still largely centralized, and too often artists have little control over their data and works. This reduction in control not only undermines their proprietary interests, but also makes it more difficult to obtain reasonable compensation and communicate directly with consumers.

Emergent technologies like blockchain and Web3 offer a compelling alternative: they provide artists total ownership of their content, enable secure and transparent transactions, and enable peer-to-peer interactions that don't involve intermediaries.

These technologies also create new income streams such as microtransactions, decentralized marketplaces, and ongoing royalties. In addition to the economic benefits, Web3 enables creativity and experimentation by being supportive of new business models and more active, stable communities. Immersive technology like augmented reality and virtual reality can also underpin these experiences, making richer modes for creators and viewers to connect.

This paper presents how blockchain, NFTs, and Web3 technologies have the potential to transform the creative industry by giving artists more control, protecting their rights, and allowing them to thrive in an ever evolving and competitive world.

The structure of this paper is as follows:

- *Chapter 2* summarizes the underlying Web3 technologies, including blockchain, Layer 1 and Layer 2 networks differentiation, and Non-Fungible Tokens

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(NFTs) for ensuring authenticity and enabling new business models.

- *Chapter 3* introduces the ChainPro Framework and the customization ChainPro for Artists (ChainPro4Artists), a Web3 solution designed exclusively for the creative community. The chapter describe the solution architecture, core features, and the smart contracts that govern its functionalities.
- *Chapter 4* describes an application scenario, explored in the context of the CHANGES project, showing how the platform is validated with real users in creative and cultural environments.
- *Chapter 5* summarizes the advantages of the solution, compared to main related works and other potential frameworks.
- *Chapter 6* concludes the paper and proposes additional scenarios and applications for ChainPro Framework

2. Blockchain Technology

Blockchain technology has emerged as a disruptive technology for cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin and facilitated the implementation of many application scenarios beyond its original purpose. Essentially, a blockchain is a distributed ledger system designed to record and secure transactions across a network of nodes. It operates in a decentralized way, utilizing a network of computers to validate and record transactions. The architecture is featured by the following key characteristics:

- *Decentralization*: no single party controls the system.

- *Consensus mechanisms*: strict rules ensure that only valid transactions are added to the chain.
- *Immutability*: once something is recorded in the chain, it can't easily be changed, which adds a layer of security.
- *Transparency*: everyone can see the full history of transactions.

2.1. Web3

The term “Web3” was coined in 2014 by Ethereum and Polkadot co-founder Gavin Wood [AW18] but the concept of Web3 started to take shape in the late 2010s to describe a new vision for the internet. This vision leverages on decentralization, blockchain technology, and the empowerment of users in controlling their data and digital assets.

In the following years, the emergence of decentralized finance (DeFi) platforms and NFTs brought Web3 concepts into the mainstream. DeFi projects offered financial services like lending, borrowing, and trading on blockchain networks, while NFTs enabled to manage the ownership and trade of unique digital assets. In addition, various projects and protocols have continued to develop the infrastructure for Web3, including decentralized storage systems (like IPFS), decentralized identity solutions, and blockchain networks designed for smart contracts.

In the meanwhile, communities and organizations focused on Web3 have emerged, with an emphasis on open-source development, decentralized governance models, and the promotion of user empowerment and privacy. The Web3 concept and technologies are changing the way the artists world operates and creating new opportunities for artists and collectors alike. The most important benefits that Web3 application can bring to the creative industry are:

- *Democratization*: Traditional creative industry is often only accessible to a selected few, due to the high cost and exclusivity of owning physical work. Web3 democratizes this process empowering the creatives.
- *Monetization*: The ability for creatives to monetize their work in new ways. With NFTs, creative works have a unique digital signature, making it one of a kind and giving it value. Artists can now sell their digital assets as NFTs, creating a new revenue stream for them.

2.2. Layer1 vs Layer 2

Ethereum and Bitcoin are considered layer 1 blockchains. Layer 1 refers to the primary layer of the blockchain where the main network operates, transactions are processed, and security is maintained. Layer 2, on the other hand, is a secondary layer built on top of Layer 1, designed to improve scalability and reduce transaction costs by processing transactions from the main blockchain while benefiting from its security.

A layer 2 refers to any off-chain network, system, or technology built on top of a layer 1 blockchain that helps extend the capabilities of the underlying base layer network. Layer 2 networks can support any blockchain to introduce improvements such as faster transaction speeds. [SSV21]

Layer 2 inherits the security of the blockchain on which it is built. Transaction data must be verified and confirmed by the underlying blockchain network rather than by a separate set of nodes.

In this way, Layer 2 blockchains can be seen as a solution to the scalability problem and cost rising, enabling fast and scalable

execution without compromising decentralization or security. Layer 2 solutions aim to relieve congestions and make blockchain networks more efficient for various applications, including DeFi and non-fungible tokens (NFTs).

The main layer 2 blockchain, built on Ethereum, is Polygon. Polygon provides a framework for building Ethereum-compatible blockchains that process transactions faster and at a lower cost than the Ethereum main net. Polygon's token (POL) is central to its ecosystem and serves various purposes, including paying transaction fees and participating in network governance. Polygon has gained prominence in the blockchain space due to its usefulness in a wide range of use cases.

Layer 1 and Layer 2 blockchain solutions offer distinct advantages and trade-offs.

Layer 1 Advantages

- Provide robust security and decentralization.
- Serve as the foundation for the entire blockchain ecosystem, hosting critical smart contracts and assets.
- Highly secure, backed by a large network of validators

Layer 2 Advantages

- Alleviate scalability issues by processing transactions off the main blockchain.
- Reduce transaction costs, making blockchain applications more accessible.

2.3. Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs)

With the emergence of Ethereum, that inserted programmatic ability in the blockchain realm, new standards started to appear. Ethereum standards provide guidelines and technical documentation for implementing new functionalities and features in smart contracts. They outline precise rules that the smart contract developer must follow to ensure the compatibility of applications within the network. One of the most prevalent standards is ERC-721 [WWB22], which describes NFTs.

Fungibility, as a concept, refers to the ability to exchange assets interchangeably, while maintaining parity of perceived value; fungible assets are interchangeable and indistinguishable from one another. Ethereum supports a standard to create fungible tokens, namely ERC-20 [WWB22]. Non fungible assets on the other hand, include the concept of uniqueness, and therefore cannot be exchanged. The ERC-721 standard was the first standard issued that set the rules for creating Non-Fungible Tokens, or NFTs. Today, new standards have appeared, like ERC-1155 [GM23], an upgrade of ERC-721, as well as standards implementing NFTs for other blockchain networks like PSP-34 for Polkadot [CK23].

Following ERC-721 standard, NFTs are unique tokens, identified by a “token id” and connected to an asset through a set of metadata. ERC-721, provides an API to:

- Create and Transfer NFTs
- Learn who owns a specific token.
- Get the supply of such tokens in the network.
- Retrieve the NFTs balance

In order to understand the importance of the NFTs it is useful to define the utility of the NFTs in different contexts and what benefits and added value they provide to their holders.

NFTs can be categorized in several types based on their utilities and in the use case applications [HOFR22]:

- Access NFTs: Provide entry to exclusive communities, events, and memberships.
- Engagement NFTs: Serve as social symbols, digital identities, and proof of attendance.
- Gamified NFTs: Include virtual wearables, in-game items, and fantasy sports cards.
- Asset NFTs: Relate to DeFi schemes, fractional ownership, and physical/digital asset guarantees.
- Dynamic NFTs: Change attributes based on user interactions or external conditions.

In the context of creative industry, Access and Asset NFTs can offer a diverse array of advantages to both creators and buyers:

- empower creators by equipping them with tools to manage the ownership and copyright of their works.
- allow creators to gain income from the reselling of their works on the secondary market with standards like ERC-2981 [Bre22]: The NFT royalty standard.
- can ensure the authenticity in the origin of works, through the transparent tracking of ownership mechanism.
- allow for a way to transact digital or physical assets, in a secure and trusted way, breaking down geographical barriers.
- give the opportunity to buyers to directly support their favourite artists and creators.

3. ChainPro for Artist – A Web3 based solution for Creative Industry

Starting from the analysis, conducted during the preliminary phase of the project, it emerged clearly how the adoption of blockchain technology is a core part for the implementation of a Web3 platform, which implements functionalities for the management of Digital Assets (including NFT creation). Blockchain technology can support the management and tracking of the entire value chain of digital assets. It: i) offers DAOs consensus mechanisms based on NFTs and smart contracts, for example, for voting on decisions to be made in digital asset market; ii) supports a fair revenue sharing model in the case of shared ownership of digital assets between different subjects; iii) provides IPR management schemes through smart contracts. Blockchain infrastructure such as Ethereum, stores the entire set of data relating to digital assets, providing reliable and unambiguous proof of the work and its owner to facilitate the enforcement of copyright. It supports NFTs through the ERC721 standard, fungible tokens with ERC20 and multi-token standards such as ERC1155. Under the perspective of scalability and cost-effectiveness of transactions Polygon is also a second-level blockchain platform that offers a multi-chain blockchain, compatible with Ethereum, which offers improvement for scalability of performance and costs reduction.

3.1. Concept and Architecture

ChainPro is a flexible and modular Web3 Framework, developed as research outcome, it is capable of:

- Facilitate the creation of Web3 applications based on blockchain technology, including the development and deployment of specific Smart Contracts

- Enable and easy and fast interaction with the main Layer 1 (Ethereum) and Layer 2 (Polygon) blockchains
- Provide a layer of standard interfaces based on open APIs for the implementation of core functionalities based on blockchain technology (Creation of NFTs, registration and use of Smart Contracts, network monitoring, etc...)

Figure 1 below shows the architecture of the ChainPro Framework.

Figure 1: ChainPro Architecture

ChainPro Architecture is structured in three main layers:

- UI Layer, for the User Experience support. It includes Web3 Apps such as the NFT Marketplace and the Blockchain Explorer
- Service Layer, that implements the core processes, captures Smart Contracts business logic and offers the interfaces with blockchain infrastructure
- Data Layer, which manages the Data governance, collection and storage

In addition, the ChainPro framework includes two additional layers for the interoperability, integration and communication aspects:

- Integration Layer, which is in charge to integrate data from IoT infrastructure, Databases or other data sources
- Communication Layer, which provide standard interfaces and communication protocols (like REST, MQTT and Kafka) for the integration of legacy platforms and external applications.

ChainPro4Artists is a platform, built upon the ChainPro Framework, which provides dedicated features for creative artists such as: Digital Asset Management, NFT Marketplace, DAO communities government. In the next section are described the main features implemented in the platform, using Smart Contracts.

3.2. Smart Contracts and main features

Smart Contracts are the core part of the ChainPro4Artists platform, since all the main features are implemented exploiting blockchain technology.

The main goal of these Smart Contracts is to keep track of all the media asset interactions expected in the ChainPro4Artists solution, including the creation or adaptation of a digital asset and

its provision to the decentralized platform on behalf of the creators, the access and download on behalf of the consumers. The smart contracts also allow for fine-grained monitoring and management of these actions as well as their translation in tokenized-based values. In addition, NFTs tokens are implemented for creating unique value for digital asset, as well for the governance and management of DAO communities in a fully democratic way.

The following Smart Contracts have been implemented:

- **Content creation and declaration of ownership.** It allows to unique identify a digital asset (via NFTs) and assign the ownership in a secure and certified way.
- **Digital asset management and definition of revenue models.** It allows to manage the digital asset distribution and selling, including revenue models and contributions from other artists or co-design resulting assets.
- **Logging Transaction.** It tracks all the transactions within the ChainPro for Artists platform (Creation of asset, Usage, NFT creations, Sales, Distribution, etc...)
- **DAO Governance.** It allows to participate in the DAO communities, creating and voting proposal for the management of the DAO itself.

4. Application Scenario

ChainPro4Artists validation belongs the context of the Spoke2 of the CHANGES project, dedicated to Creativity and Intangible Cultural Heritage solutions. Initial tests have already demonstrated outstanding potentialities for the specific domain. The main goal of the CHANGES Spoke2 is to support creative ecosystems in developing new solutions for supporting the Cultural and Creative Sector, in particular in the fields of human creativity linked with intangible cultural heritage and performing arts.

ChainPro4Artists is aimed at being adopted by end-users in the context of performing arts, music, audiovisual media, design, and fashion, craftsmanship. The end-users, already involved in a preliminary stage for user-centred design of specific features of the platform, will be also involved in a validation test of the platform, to evaluate the usability and accessibility, in particular for the blockchain related technologies. A specific focus will be dedicated to User Experience (UX).

5. Related works and ChainPro4Artists advantages

The development of Web3 solutions has been supported by a variety of frameworks such as Truffle, Hardhat, and Moralis, which provide essential tools for smart contract development, testing, and blockchain interaction [XXY*25]. While these platforms have significantly contributed to the Web3 ecosystem, they often present limitations in terms of integration capabilities, user interface support, and ease of use for non-technical stakeholders.

ChainPro Framework introduces a comprehensive and modular solution that addresses these gaps by offering a multi-layered architecture supporting the full stack including UI components, service logic, data governance, and interoperability with external systems. In addition, ChainPro supports seamless interaction with both Layer 1 (Ethereum) and Layer 2 (Polygon) blockchains and provides standardized interfaces for core blockchain functionalities such as NFT creation and smart contract management. Its native capability of supporting standard protocols

like REST, MQTT, and Kafka, further enhances interoperability with legacy systems and IoT infrastructures.

Its modular design enables rapid development of complex Web3 applications, while its extension, ChainPro4Artists, demonstrates its versatility by offering tailored features for creative artists such as digital asset management, NFT marketplaces, and DAO governance. This holistic approach makes ChainPro a powerful and accessible framework for both developers and domain-specific platforms.

6. Conclusion and other applications

Web3 platforms like ChainPro4Artists has the potentiality to be a game-changer for Creative Industry and artists. It offers the main characteristics of blockchain technology, ensuring a fully decentralized innovative approach for the creation and distribution of creative contents and bundling those features in an easy-to-use approach for the actors. This approach can overcome barriers observed in domains like Creative Industry where creators could suffer of lack of knowledge in blockchain technologies.

In addition, the flexibility of the ChainPro Framework allows to extend the adoption of these technologies to other contexts. About that, an experimentation in the tourism context is ongoing. In the context of Spoke9 CHANGES activities, a Smart Tourist Marketplace has been successfully integrated with the ChainPro Framework for experimenting the usage of NFTs for loyalty incentive circuit and tokenization of user-generated content, providing the possibility to manage and acquire NFTs and Tokens within the Smart Tourist Marketplace, improving the stakeholder engagement and protect IPR for the user-generated contents.

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